

FORMATION OF ATTITUDES TOWARDS LEARNING IN YOUNGER SCHOOL-AGE STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550211>

Abstract. *The thinking of children of younger school age will still be practical, concrete thinking, but in the process of education, such concrete thinking of children becomes more complex and meaningful than the concrete thinking of children of preschool age. At school, the student learns to compare, analyze and synthesize more and more complex things and what he perceives, and not only phenomena, but also objects and phenomena that he imagines.*

Keyword: *perception, small school age, analysis, synthesis, interest.*

The younger school age period includes the age range of students in grades 1-4. During this period, it can be observed that certain changes occur in the child's psyche. As soon as the child first steps to the threshold of school, a number of psychological difficulties begin to arise in him. During the junior school period, the child's first step to the threshold of the school is the beginning of educational activity in it. It is required to spend this period interesting, touching for the child. In the process of a child's schooling, the ability to abstract begins to grow in him. At the time of the transition from a practical portrait count to an abstract calculation in mathematics lessons, as well as during the lessons of the native language, this ability grows especially noticeably. In the process of studying other disciplines, this ability grows even more. The child learns to analyze, abstract and compare, to distinguish between significant signs of things and insignificant signs by means of exercise, to draw conclusions without looking at important signs of a subject, event. The thinking of younger school-age students differs from preschool children and adolescents in their peculiarities in the use of various methods of logical thinking, reasoning, judgment and conclusion, comparison analysis. Teaching in the process of education to contemplative operations, independent thinking is a guarantee of achieving perfection for students of younger school age. A child 6-11 years old can think logically, but this age is considered a period when he is censored for education, relying mainly on what he sees.

In elementary school, children from the first grade will be able to master a large number of different concepts-grammar, arithmetic, nature, as well as socio — political ones. The range of concepts that students master is largely determined by the curriculum, which is compiled for each class in different disciplines. Concepts with a certain scientific content are given to students in a logically expressed form. Readers also learn to describe their concepts by describing their content and showing signs regarding their gender and species. Readers describe, compare, characterize and illustrate with examples when they cannot describe concepts and rules, or when they cannot be described. N.S. According to Leites' reasoning, as a person grows older, the level of mental development increases somewhat, while the property of ugliness decreases somewhat. The readability of children of small school age, of course, is higher than that of adolescents and adolescents, but the mental development of adolescents and adolescents is higher than that of Primary School students. This situation is considered to be associated with the leading activity of students of younger school age – with the presence of studies, but with the fact that cognitive processes have not yet developed comprehensively.

The mental development of children in the younger school period is determined by social factors. Individ changes under the influence of social relations. The transition of a child to study at school on a regular basis leads to the development of all his cognitive processes and, in itself, to a change in his opinion, attitude towards things-phenomena in the surrounding life, in which learning activity determines changes in the development of the psyche of children in the younger school period. A child who comes to school for the first time does not fully understand the fundamental essence and function of his activity, but considers that everyone should go to school. Diligence, following the instructions of adults. will go into training with. After a certain period of time, as the impression of poetic moments decreases, the external signs of the school lose their relevance, and the child realizes that reading is everyday mental work. Then the child will be disappointed in his studies if he does not have the skills of mental work, a feeling of hopelessness will arise in him, and the teacher, in order to prevent such a situation, should give the child information about the difference in education from the game, the fun and prepare him for this activity. The features that are contained in the course of the study activity serve as the basis for the further development of the child. Studying at school creates conditions for the rapid development and qualitative content of children's cognitive needs, the emergence of their active interest in the surrounding life, and the acquisition of new knowledge and skills. Gradually, the child begins to learn to control his perception, attention and memory, owning his own psychic processes. The educational activities of younger school-age students are governed by a system of multilevel motives that are complex. The motives of educational activity indicate why students are studying. Social motives prevail in children who come to the first grade of school. These motives are those that are associated with the acquisition of a new position among those around them, socially significant and evaluated activities. But by the end of the first grade, most students begin to look at their school obligations with irresponsibility. This is due to several reasons:

1) the child has now become a reader, the desire to become a reader has been satisfied. This happens even if he does nothing to hold the status. In the development of children's thinking and speech, the importance of sound reflection and the use of this method in the learning process is great. Reasoning aloud and substantiating one's own solution serve to increase mental qualities, and a person develops an analysis and understanding of his reasoning and behavior. In students of younger school age, the possibilities of mastering mental and educational material are considered much higher. In a properly organized education, children of this age can understand and assimilate more knowledge in relation to the knowledge specified in the high school program. Another of the peculiarities of the educational activity of children of younger school age is that from this period, the first signs of non-assimilation of educational material are noticeable. A positive attitude towards learning comes towards the end of the junior school period, when a slight decline is noticeable. Interest in educational activities – rises in grades 1-2 and decreases in grades 3-4. In the decline in interest in educational activities, the teacher's articulation of the finished material and the ustanovka of students ' memorization prevail, and the activity of students is in the nature of imitation. Students in grades 3-4 usually do not like to retell what was read, copy-write an exercise written on the board, memorize rules and poems, and, on the contrary, love to independently solve examples and issues, observe natural phenomena, draw and do things from plasticine and clay. In other words, younger school-age students are more interested in jobs where there is an opportunity for Initiative and independence. As one of the reasons for the decline in interest in studying at a

small school age, V.A.Sukhomlinsky believes that a low grade is put a lot by the teacher, which is a decrease in interest in reading in a child and a decrease in confidence in his capabilities.

The fact that in primary school students all elements of educational activity are formed and can be performed independently means that reading as a leading activity has fulfilled its task. The educational activities of students of younger school age include the following in their composition:

- skills to independently find common ways of solving problems;
- distinguish, find and Master educational tasks;
- be able to adequately assess and control oneself and one's own activities;
- being able to self-manage in activities;
- being able to use the rules of logical thinking;
- being able to acquire and use different forms of generalization;
- being able to participate in collective activities;
- having a high level of independent creative activity.

But in most cases, the problem of teaching children to practical skills, skills of reading, writing, counting, is that the educational activity of students of younger school age is at the forefront of school practice.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the main task of primary school educational activity is to teach students to “read”, to gain knowledge. In the mental development of children of younger school age, serious changes occur in the influence of Education. These changes prepare them for the transition to adolescence, which is a responsible period of their lives.

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